

Effectiveness of Incorporating MCQ in Orthodontic Lectures on Short Term Knowledge Retention of BDS Students

MUHAMMAD AZEEM¹, SABIR ALI², AMBREEN SHAUKAT³, ARFAN UL HAQ⁴

ABSTRACT

Aim: To determine the effect of incorporating multiple choice questions (MCQ) in orthodontic lectures on knowledge retention of BDS students.

Methods: Present study was conducted on 40 BDS final year students of Dental section, Faisalabad Medical University. Students were divided into 2 groups of 20 each. One group received a traditional didactic lecture and other received the same lecture integrated with at least 3 MCQs. Students completed an assessment of MCQ before and immediately after the lecture to determine the effect on knowledge retention. ANOVA test was used for comparison of MCQ scores in both the groups. The level of significance was determined at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: Results showed that incorporating MCQ in the orthodontic lectures led to statistically significant increase in MCQ scores immediately after the lecture.

Conclusion: The incorporation of MCQ in orthodontic lectures does lead to a significant increase in short term knowledge retention of BDS students.

Keywords: MCQs; Orthodontic; Medical education.

INTRODUCTION

Traditional didactic lectures are basically a part of teacher centric teaching which is devoid of engaging students in learning process¹. In higher education there is increase trend toward switching from teacher centric teaching to student centric teaching²⁻⁵. Student centric teaching having component of active interactions is helpful for learner's development⁶.

Effective learning depends on many factors⁷⁻¹⁰ such as; outcome focused approach, student centric learning, teaching environment, motivation of students and teachers, and student-teacher interactions. Teachers are concerned about student-teacher interaction while delivering lecture to large group of students.¹¹ The audience response system is one of the methods that can be used to engage large group of students while delivering lecture as it allows teachers to get immediate assessment and evaluation¹²⁻¹⁵.

The main disadvantage of audience response system is its cost. Incorporation of Multiple choice questions (MCQ) in lectures can also be used as a tool to engage large group of students while delivering lecture as it can allow teachers to get immediate assessment and evaluation¹¹. This may also allows teachers to get feedback into how to improve their teaching effectiveness and may also allows students to improve their knowledge retention.

The aim of present study was to determine the effect of incorporating multiple choice questions (MCQ) in orthodontic lectures on knowledge retention of BDS students.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This randomized control trial was conducted at Faisalabad medical university, Pakistan from July 2017 to Feb 2018. Non-probability purposive sampling technique was used. The sample size was based on the total number of fresh BDS students that just got promoted from third year BDS after the final summative assessment¹⁶.

Inclusion Criteria

Fresh final year students of BDS

No prior orthodontic teaching or knowledge

Exclusion Criteria

Detained students or students repeating the final year
Prior orthodontic teaching sessions

According to the selection criteria, 40 fresh BDS final year students of Dental section, Faisalabad Medical University were selected. Students were divided randomly into 2 groups of 20 each, using random number table method.

One group received a traditional didactic lecture and other received the same lecture integrated with at least 3 MCQ. Students completed an assessment of MCQ before and immediately after the lecture to determine the effect on knowledge retention. The lecture in second group consisted of 50 slides of which 3 slides were MCQ based. The topic of lecture was basic definitions of occlusion, normal occlusion,

¹Assistant Professor Orthodontics, Faisalabad Medical University,

²Dental Surgeon, RHC Moongi Banglow, Toba Tek Singh.

³Dental Surgeon, RHC Makhdoom Rasheed, Multan.

⁴Dean & Professor Orthodontics, Faisalabad Medical University,
Correspondence to Dr. Muhammad Azeem:
Email:dental.concepts@hotmail.com, Cell: +92-345-8409007

ideal occlusion and malocclusions. Teaching delivery was standardized so that the teaching material conveyed to BDS students by the teacher was as similar as possible. Data collected was analyzed by using software SPSS version 20.0. ANOVA test was used for comparison of MCQ scores in both the groups. The level of significance was determined at $p \leq 0.05$.

RESULTS

The difference in mean MCQ between the groups at baseline was statistically insignificant ($P=0.087$). (Table I). The difference in mean MCQ between the groups at post lecture stage was statistically significant ($P=0.000$). The improvement in MCQ scores in both the groups from baseline to post lecture stage increases statistically significantly ($P=0.000$). (Table I)

Table 1: Comparison of MCQ scores in two groups at different times

	Baseline		Post lecture		Difference		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Conventional lecture	5.5	2.2	7.7	2.1	2.2	1.6	0.000
MCQ integrated lecture	7.3	1.6	12.1	1.7	4.8	1.7	0.000
Difference	1.8	0.7	4.4	0.5	2.6	1.4	
Significance	0.087		0.000		0.000		

DISCUSSION

Traditional didactic lectures are basically a part of teacher centric teaching but in higher education there is increase trend toward switching to student centric teaching.¹⁻³ Effective learning depends on many factors. Teachers are concerned about student-teacher interaction while delivering lecture to large group of students. Incorporation of Multiple choice questions (MCQ) in lectures can also be used as a tool to engage large group of students while delivering lecture as it can allow teachers to get immediate assessment and evaluation and may also allows students to improve their knowledge retention¹¹.

The aim of present study was to determine the effect of incorporating multiple choice questions in orthodontic lectures on knowledge retention of BDS students. The sample size was based on the total number of fresh BDS students that just got promoted from third year BDS after the final summative assessment¹⁶.

Present study was conducted on 40 BDS final year students of Dental section, Faisalabad Medical University. Students were divided into 2 groups of 20 each. One group received a traditional didactic lecture and other received the same lecture integrated with at least 3 MCQs. Students completed an assessment of MCQ before and immediately after the lecture to determine the effect on knowledge retention.

Results showed that the difference in mean MCQ between the groups at baseline was statistically insignificant. The difference in mean MCQ between the groups at post lecture stage was statistically significant. The improvement in MCQ scores in both the groups from baseline to post lecture stage increases statistically significantly.

Thus it was found that the incorporation of MCQ in orthodontic lectures does lead to a significant increase in short term knowledge retention of BDS students. Results are in agreement with findings of Brady and Pampllett, both of them, found that MCQ can test large group of students, in a short time^{17,18}. The present study shows that there is key role of assessments for learning, and the importance of assessment, not at the end but for educational improvement^{19,20}. Therefore the implications of present study influence not only on BDS students, but also on orthodontic lecturers.

Limitation of current study is small sample size, further large scale studies are suggested to determine the effect of incorporating multiple choice questions in orthodontic lectures on knowledge retention of BDS students.

CONCLUSION

The incorporation of MCQ in orthodontic lectures does lead to a significant increase in short term knowledge retention of BDS students.

REFERENCES

1. Richards JC, Rodgers TS. Approaches and methods in language teaching. Cambridge university press; 2014 Apr 16.
2. Freeman S, Eddy SL, McDonough M, Smith MK, Okoroafor N, Jordt H, Wenderoth MP. Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences. 2014 Jun 10;111(23):8410-5.
3. Gilboy MB, Heinerichs S, Pazzaglia G. Enhancing student engagement using the flipped classroom. Journal of nutrition education and behavior. 2015 Jan 1;47(1):109-14.

4. Miller A. Games centered approaches in teaching children & adolescents: Systematic review of associated student outcomes. *Journal of teaching in physical education*. 2015 Jan;34(1):36-58.
5. Bradshaw M, Hultquist BL. Innovative teaching strategies in nursing and related health professions. Jones & Bartlett Publishers; 2016 Jul 29.
6. Bovill C, Cook-Sather A, Felten P, Millard L, Moore-Cherry N. Addressing potential challenges in co-creating learning and teaching: Overcoming resistance, navigating institutional norms and ensuring inclusivity in student-staff partnerships. *Higher Education*. 2016 Feb 1;71(2):195-208.
7. Chappuis J. Seven strategies of assessment for learning. Pearson; 2015.
8. Hwang GJ, Lai CL, Wang SY. Seamless flipped learning: a mobile technology-enhanced flipped classroom with effective learning strategies. *Journal of Computers in Education*. 2015 Dec 1;2(4):449-73.
9. Jan SR, Ullah F, Ali H, Khan F. Enhanced and effective learning through mobile learning an insight into students perception of mobile learning at university level. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science, Engineering and Technology (IJSRSET)*, Print ISSN. 2016:2395-1990.
10. Cheng D, Price B, Cohen S, Brown MS. Effective learning-based illuminant estimation using simple features. In Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition 2015 (pp. 1000-1008).
11. Donnelly C. The use of case based multiple choice questions for assessing large group teaching: implications on student's learning. *Irish Journal of Academic Practice*. 2014;3(1):12.
12. Hunsu NJ, Adesope O, Bayly DJ. A meta-analysis of the effects of audience response systems (clicker-based technologies) on cognition and affect. *Computers & Education*. 2016 Mar 1;94:102-19.
13. Heaslip G, Donovan P, Cullen JG. Student response systems and learner engagement in large classes. *Active Learning in Higher Education*. 2014 Mar;15(1):11-24.
14. Lürer S, Aebi C, Tekian A. In-Course Evaluation via Mobile Device Audience Response System—a Pilot Project in Postgraduate Medical Education at a University Children's Hospital.
15. Wolff M, Wagner MJ, Poznanski S, Schiller J, Santen S. Not another boring lecture: engaging learners with active learning techniques. *Journal of Emergency Medicine*. 2015 Jan 1;48(1):85-93.
16. Robson N, Popat H, Richmond S, Farnell DJ. Effectiveness of an audience response system on orthodontic knowledge retention of undergraduate dental students—a randomised control trial. *Journal of orthodontics*. 2015 Oct 2;42(4):307-14.
17. Brady AM. Assessment of learning with multiple-choice questions. *Nurse Education in Practice*. 2005 Jul 1;5(4):238-42.
18. Pamphlett R, Farnill D. Effect of anxiety on performance in multiple choice examination. *Medical education*. 1995 Jul 1;29(4):297-302.
19. Banta TW. *Assessment in Practice: Putting Principles To Work on College Campuses*. Jossey-Bass Higher and Adult Education Series. Jossey-Bass Inc., Publishers, 350 Sansome St., San Francisco, CA 94104; 1996.
20. Donnelly C. The use of case based multiple choice questions for assessing large group teaching: implications on student's learning. *Irish Journal of Academic Practice*. 2014;3(1):12.